

CHARACTERISTICS OF SERVICE POSITIONING STRATEGIES IN TOURISM ENTERPRISES

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *In this article, for the development of a marketing strategy in a tourist enterprise, the selection of the target market and the positioning strategy, the establishment of relations with consumers, the development of new goods, and the promotion are considered.*

Keywords: *Tourism enterprise, service, strategy, position, target market, consumer, product.*

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА СТРАТЕГИЙ ПОЗИЦИОНИРОВАНИЯ УСЛУГ В ТУРИСТСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ

Аннотация. *В данной статье для разработки маркетинговой стратегии туристского предприятия рассматриваются выбор целевого рынка и стратегии позиционирования, установление отношений с потребителями, разработка новых товаров, продвижение.*

Ключевые слова: *туристское предприятие, услуга, стратегия, позиция, целевой рынок, потребитель, продукт.*

After selecting a target segment (or segments), a tourism firm must decide how to position itself in each segment. The importance of this decision is that it serves as the basis for developing a marketing program. Positioning determines how the firm is perceived by target customers. It can be described as follows:

Positioning is the development and creation of the image of the product in the mind of the buyer in such a way that it occupies a worthy place in the mind of the competitor.

To develop a marketing strategy in a tourist enterprise, the selection of the target market and the strategy of positioning is the basis for establishing relations with consumers, developing new goods, promotion and others.

Thus, the positioning strategy is a means of implementing the differentiation strategy. Usually at this stage there are questions like:

-What are the features and benefits (real or perceived) that buyers look at most positively?

- What are the positions of competing tourist companies regarding these features and benefits?

- the desire of potential buyers in a certain segment-What is the best position to take, taking into account their preferences and the positions taken by competitors?

-what marketing tools are best suited to take and defend the chosen position?

A differentiated marketing strategy requires high investment, production and management costs, so it is necessary for large tourism firms.

Differentiation of tourism services is another opportunity to enter different markets. It is primarily based on carrying out a diversification strategy in the distribution of services.

A concentrated marketing strategy requires tourism firms to focus on a profitable segment of the market, that is, one or more segments. A tourism firm approaches this market segment with a targeted marketing program with one or more tourism products. Ultimately, this

strategy is consistent with the concept of a niche market, that is, it is necessary to work in such a market segment that the tourism product is considered to be the most suitable for this tour company and its delivery capabilities. A concentrated marketing strategy is suitable for most small and medium-sized tourist companies, because it does not require large enough financial means to work in all market segments.

Market positioning is a technology for determining the position of a tourist product in certain market segments. The purpose of positioning is to research the existing and emerging opinions, analyze the attitude of buyers or their group to product parameters, and create such a product position by conducting marketing measures to ensure the competitive advantage of the product in this segment of the target market.

In order to effectively position the product, it is necessary to establish and study the important characteristics of supply and demand, the influence of factors that are considered to be relevant in making a purchase decision. Determining factors can be tourist product quality, level of quality, reliability, energy consumption, design and other indicators of product competitiveness.

Correct organization of market positioning is a condition for effective development of a marketing plan and complex.

Based on the study of the capacity of the tourist market, the dynamics of its growth, which is considered as the basis for the formation of production forces and the construction of the distribution network for the sale of tourist products, will be determined. It should be taken into account that the market capacity should be sufficient, that is, the results of the market activity should be achieved, the costs related to market operation should be increased, and the planned profit should be guaranteed.

The study of the structure of the attractiveness of the segment includes the study of the level of competition, the competitiveness of existing products, the attitude to customers, the stability of the segment's demand for the offered and existing goods, the necessity and possibility of introducing a completely new product to the market that satisfies the needs of existing buyers.

Determining the goals and resources of the organization necessary to achieve the objectives of the growing segment is of strategic importance, and it is necessary to determine the adequacy or burden of the potential resources for the implementation of the long-term goals of the travel company in accordance with the current goals and, accordingly, to work in the target market. For this, it is appropriate to calculate the risk. Special marketing and consulting companies can be invited to calculate the organization's risk.

Market positioning is a technology for determining the product's position in specific market segments. The purpose of positioning is to research the existing and emerging opinions, to analyze the attitude of buyers or their group to the parameters of the product, to establish the position of the tourist product in this segment of the target market by means of marketing measures to ensure the competitive advantage of the product.

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